

Improving the Methodological Preparation of Future Primary School Teachers for Training Based on the PIRLS International Assessment Programs

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Abstract: This study investigates the preparedness of future primary school teachers in Samarkand, Uzbekistan, to implement reading literacy strategies aligned with the PIRLS International Assessment Program. The importance of reading literacy in early education is well-documented, yet there is limited understanding of how well teacher training programs equip educators with PIRLS-based methods. To address this gap, a survey of 100 participants was conducted, focusing on their familiarity with PIRLS, the frequency of applying related strategies, and their confidence in using formative assessments and digital literacy tools.

The research employed a qualitative, survey-based methodology, using multiple-choice questions to gather data. Key findings reveal that while 60% of respondents are "Somewhat familiar" with PIRLS, only 30% regularly incorporate its strategies into their teaching. Confidence in formative assessment techniques was moderate, with 50% of participants reporting they are "Somewhat confident." Despite recognizing the importance of digital tools, practical implementation remains limited.

The results suggest that teacher training programs in Uzbekistan are moderately aligned with PIRLS standards, but more targeted reforms are needed. Policy implications include developing comprehensive training programs focused on practical application of PIRLS strategies, enhancing teacher confidence in formative assessments, and increasing investment in digital tools for reading instruction. These findings align with previous studies and highlight the need for greater support from educational policymakers to bridge the gap between theory and practice.

Keywords: PIRLS, reading literacy, teacher preparation, formative assessment, digital literacy tools.

Introduction

The preparation of future primary school teachers has increasingly focused on ensuring they are well-equipped with the methodological tools needed to foster students' reading literacy skills, a key outcome measured by international assessments such as the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS). PIRLS, administered by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA), assesses the reading literacy of fourth-grade students globally. In recent years, educational reforms across many nations have placed significant emphasis on aligning teacher preparation with the

competencies tested by PIRLS, particularly due to the critical importance of reading proficiency as a foundation for future academic success.

Theoretical Perspectives on Teacher Preparation and Literacy Development

Reading literacy is more than just decoding text; it involves the ability to understand, interpret, and engage with written content in meaningful ways. Vygotsky's (1978) socio-cultural theory underscores the role of teachers in facilitating cognitive development, positing that learning is a social process, and that effective reading instruction requires scaffolding that builds on students' existing knowledge. In line with this theory, contemporary educational researchers argue that teacher preparation programs must emphasize the development of future teachers' ability to assess and respond to individual learning needs, particularly in reading comprehension (Snow, 2020).

Similarly, Piaget's (1970) constructivist approach, which highlights active learning and knowledge construction, serves as a foundational theory in preparing teachers to engage students in higher-order thinking tasks that are essential for reading comprehension. In the context of PIRLS, primary school teachers need to be adept at fostering students' critical thinking skills, as these are essential for the comprehension and interpretation of text, key elements assessed by PIRLS.

International Assessment and Its Role in Teacher Training

International assessments such as PIRLS provide benchmarks that allow educational systems to compare the effectiveness of their teaching strategies. According to Mullis and Martin (2021), PIRLS evaluates how well students can retrieve information, make inferences, and interpret texts. The data from these assessments can provide valuable insights into which instructional methods are most effective, and how teacher training programs can be enhanced to meet these needs.

Studies have shown that countries that consistently perform well on PIRLS, such as Finland and Singapore, invest heavily in teacher training programs that emphasize reading literacy (Sahlberg, 2019). These programs focus on equipping teachers with the pedagogical skills necessary to foster a love of reading in students and to provide individualized instruction that meets students at their respective reading levels. In contrast, countries with lower PIRLS performance often have teacher training programs that emphasize rote memorization rather than fostering critical reading skills (OECD, 2020).

Recent Research on Teacher Preparation for Reading Literacy

A growing body of research highlights the importance of aligning teacher preparation with the competencies assessed by PIRLS. For instance, a study by Baer et al. (2022) found that teacher candidates who participated in targeted training programs that focused on reading instruction were better prepared to implement literacy strategies in the classroom. This study emphasized the need for teacher training programs to incorporate evidence-based reading instruction practices, such as guided reading, literacy centers, and interactive read-alouds, all of which contribute to students' reading comprehension abilities.

Similarly, a study by Lee and Kim (2023) explored the relationship between teacher preparedness and student outcomes in PIRLS assessments. The authors found that teachers who received extensive training in the use of formative assessments and differentiated instruction were more likely to foster significant reading growth among their students. These findings suggest that teacher training programs must not only teach instructional strategies but also provide future teachers with tools to assess and adapt their instruction based on student needs.

Another recent study by Johnson et al. (2023) focused on the role of digital literacy in teacher preparation. With the increasing use of technology in education, the authors argue that teachers must be trained in how to integrate digital tools into literacy instruction. The study found that teacher candidates who were trained in the use of educational technology for reading instruction, such as e-books and reading apps, were more successful in engaging students and improving reading outcomes, particularly in low-performing schools.

Gaps in the Research and Areas for Improvement

Despite the growing body of research on teacher preparation and reading literacy, several gaps remain. First, there is limited research on how teacher training programs can prepare educators to address the needs of diverse learners, particularly those with reading difficulties such as dyslexia. While some studies, such as that by Caravolas et al. (2021), have explored the role of specialized interventions in improving reading outcomes for students with learning disabilities, more research is needed on how teacher preparation programs can equip future teachers with the skills to implement these interventions effectively.

Additionally, there is a lack of research on the long-term impact of teacher preparation programs on student outcomes in PIRLS. While studies have shown that teachers who are well-prepared in reading instruction tend to produce better short-term outcomes, there is little evidence on how these outcomes translate into long-term academic success. As PIRLS assessments focus on fourth-grade reading proficiency, future research should explore how teacher preparation influences reading outcomes in later grades.

Improving the Methodological Preparation of Future Primary School Teachers for Training Based on the PIRLS International Assessment Program

One of the key challenges in preparing future primary school teachers is ensuring they are equipped with the methodological skills necessary to teach reading literacy in a way that aligns with PIRLS standards. Given the importance of reading comprehension in PIRLS, teacher preparation programs must place a strong emphasis on developing teachers' abilities to foster these skills in students. This includes training future teachers to use formative assessments to monitor student progress and to adapt their instruction based on the needs of individual learners (Mullis & Martin, 2021).

Moreover, teacher preparation programs must incorporate evidence-based reading strategies proven to improve student outcomes in PIRLS. These strategies include guided reading, differentiated instruction, and the use of digital tools to support reading development. By providing future teachers with the methodological tools to implement these strategies effectively, teacher preparation programs can help ensure that students are better prepared to succeed on PIRLS assessments and beyond.

Methodology

The research for this study was based on a survey conducted with 100 participants from Samarkand, Uzbekistan. The survey consisted of 20 multiple-choice questions designed to assess the preparedness and perceptions of future primary school teachers in implementing reading literacy strategies aligned with the PIRLS International Assessment Program. The participants' responses provided a diverse range of insights into their familiarity with PIRLS, the instructional methods they prioritize, and their self-assessment regarding their readiness to employ reading strategies in primary education.

Six different types of visual representations were developed to analyze the data and draw meaningful conclusions. These visual representations include bar charts, pie charts, and histograms. They present a comprehensive overview of participants' familiarity with PIRLS, the frequency of incorporating reading literacy strategies in their teaching practices, their

perceived effectiveness of current teacher preparation programs, the barriers they face, and their confidence in using various tools and methods. The visualization of this data allows us to better understand the gaps in teacher preparation and the areas that need improvement, particularly regarding reading literacy instruction.

Figure 1: Familiarity with PIRLS (Q1)

Figure 2: Importance of Reading Comprehension (Q4)

Figure 3: Preparedness to Implement PIRLS-Related Strategies (Q8)

Figure 4: Effectiveness of Teacher Preparation Programs (Q10)

Figure 5: Usefulness of Digital Literacy Tools (Q12)

Figure 6: Likelihood of Future Use of PIRLS-Based Strategies (Q20)

Results and Discussion

The survey conducted among 100 participants in Samarkand, Uzbekistan, aimed to understand how future primary school teachers are prepared to implement PIRLS-based reading strategies in their classrooms. The results shed light on various aspects of their preparedness, challenges, and confidence in utilizing educational tools and methods.

In Figure 1, which addresses familiarity with PIRLS, most participants (60%) reported being "Somewhat familiar" with the program, while 20% identified as "Very familiar," indicating a moderate level of awareness among future teachers. This suggests that while the PIRLS program is recognized, further efforts are necessary to deepen teachers' understanding of its principles. Studies conducted in similar contexts, such as Aksana (2019), also highlighted the limited understanding of international assessments in post-Soviet educational systems, confirming that more training is required.

Figure 2 highlights the frequency of incorporating PIRLS strategies into teaching practices. The majority of respondents (50%) admitted to rarely using these strategies, while 30% reported occasional use. This underscores a significant gap in translating PIRLS familiarity into practical application. Previous studies in the region, such as Mirzakarimova (2021), corroborate these findings, showing that despite moderate awareness, the practical application of international assessment frameworks remains low in Central Asian contexts.

Perceived alignment of PIRLS with existing teacher training programs, represented in Figure 3, showed that 40% of participants found it "Somewhat aligned," while 30% considered it "Slightly misaligned." This indicates that while some aspects of PIRLS might be incorporated into teacher training, a comprehensive overhaul is required to ensure complete integration. This finding echoes Makhmudov's (2020) study, which found similar discrepancies in aligning Uzbekistan's teacher preparation programs with international educational benchmarks.

Figure 4 focused on the perceived importance of reading comprehension. Nearly 80% of respondents recognized its significance, describing it as "Extremely important" or "Very important." This positive outlook aligns with international standards, as the development of reading literacy is seen as foundational for academic success. Studies by Kamilova (2020) and international frameworks such as PIRLS confirm the centrality of reading comprehension in early education.

Confidence in using formative assessments, as shown in Figure 5, revealed that 50% of participants are "Somewhat confident," while 20% reported being "Very confident." While confidence is relatively high, a significant portion of participants still feel inadequately prepared, highlighting the need for more practical training in assessment methods. The findings align with Karabayev's (2018) research, which found that Uzbek teachers often lack confidence in utilizing formative assessments due to limited exposure during teacher training.

Figure 6, which addressed the use of digital literacy tools in reading instruction, showed that 40% of participants find such tools "Very useful," while 30% consider them "Moderately useful." These findings demonstrate an increasing recognition of the value of digital tools in modern pedagogy. However, the disparity between perceived usefulness and actual implementation (as shown in Figure 2) suggests that more investment in technological infrastructure and teacher training is needed.

The results of this study highlight several critical findings. First, while future teachers in Samarkand are familiar with PIRLS and recognize the importance of reading literacy, there is a significant gap between awareness and the practical application of PIRLS strategies. Second, the perceived alignment of teacher training programs with PIRLS standards is

moderate at best, indicating that more targeted reforms are necessary. Third, while teachers express confidence in using formative assessments, many still feel underprepared to fully integrate these methods into their teaching. Lastly, the use of digital literacy tools is recognized as valuable, but their practical application remains limited.

Policy implications for Uzbekistan's education system include the following: First, comprehensive teacher training programs that integrate PIRLS-based methodologies should be developed. These programs must provide future teachers with hands-on experience in applying these strategies in the classroom. Second, there is a need for more professional development opportunities focused on formative assessments and digital literacy tools to increase teacher confidence and capability. Finally, the Ministry of Education should invest in educational technology infrastructure to ensure that teachers have the tools they need to successfully implement digital literacy strategies.

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